

Photogalvanic effect : Comparative studies in three dyes Rhodamine B, Methylene blue and Safranin

K. R. Genwa*, Mahaveer and Indra Prakash

Department of Chemistry, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur-342 001. Rajasthan. India

E-mail : krg2004@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : The photogalvanic effect was studied in photogalvanic cell containing ascorbic acid as a reductant, Methylene blue, Safranin and Rhodamine B as photosensitizers for solar energy conversion and storage point of view. The conversion efficiency for Methylene blue, Safranin and Rhodamine B were 0.83, 0.65 and 0.51% and storage capacity 165.0, 115.0, 45.0 min respectively. The effect of variations of various parameters on electrical output and *i-V* characteristics of the cell were observed and a mechanism for generation of photocurrent has also been proposed.

Keywords : Photogalvanic effect, dyes, Rhodamine B, methylene blue, Safranin.

We have reported some photogalvanic systems with reasonably good amount of electrical output and storage capacity¹. Now it is worthwhile to interpret the observations to arrive a satisfactory mechanism of photocurrent generation, cell performance, conversion efficiency of the cell and to decide the role of various type of micelles in photogalvanic cell.

Results and discussion

It was observed that a constant potential was obtained with these three systems at different time periods and the rate of change of potential are in order :

Rhodamine B > Safranin > Methylene blue

whereas on removing the source of illumination the rate of change of potential is in order :

Methylene blue > Safranin > Rhodamine B

On the basis of observed results, the most efficient photogalvanic cell is the cell with Ascorbic acid-Methylene blue system followed by the cell containing Ascorbic acid-Safranin and Ascorbic acid-Rhodamine B systems.

It was observed that current of all these photogalvanic systems increases rapidly to a maximum value (i_{max}) within first few minutes of illumination. On further illumination current increases slowly attaining a stable value at equilibrium (i_{eq}) which falls rapidly on removing the source of illumination. On the basis of observation it was clear that the current generated in these photogalvanic cells is

in following order :

Methylene blue > Safranin > Rhodamine B

The most efficient system is Ascorbic acid-Methylene blue followed by Ascorbic acid-Safranin and Ascorbic acid-Rhodamine B from generation of current point of view.

The changes in pH value effects the values of photopotential and photocurrent. It was further observed that these systems have the workable range in strongly alkaline medium (pH = 12.8-13.2). The pH for optimum condition for each system has a relation with the nature of dyes (MB, SF, RB). This may be due to the availability of the reductant (Ascorbic acid) in a better donor form (in ionic form) than its unionized form.

Effect of variation of diffusion length on the electrical output (i_{max} , i_{eq}) and initial rate of generation of current of the photogalvanic cell were observed by using the H-cell of different dimensions. The diffusion length (distance between the electrodes) greatly affects all the three systems. It was observed that in the first few minutes of illumination there was a sharp increase in the photocurrent and then there is a gradual decrease to a stable value of photocurrent this behaviour of photocurrent indicates an initial rapid reaction followed by a slow rate determining step.

The oxidized form of the reductant is formed only in the illuminated chamber and if it is considered to be the electroactive species in dark chamber, then it must diffuse from the illuminated chamber to the dark chamber to

accept an electron from the electrode. As a consequence, the maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) and rate of generation of photocurrent should increase with an increase in diffusion length, but it is not observed to be independent with respect to change in diffusion length, but it is not observed experimentally. The value of (i_{eq}) was also observed to be independent with respect to change in diffusion length (rather it decreases slightly). Therefore, it may be concluded that the main electroactive species are the leuco or semi leuco form of dyes (photosensitizers) and the dye in the illuminated and the dark chamber, respectively. However, the reductant and its oxidation product act only as electron carriers in the path.

i-V characteristics of the cell :

The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (i_{sc}) of all these systems were measured with the help of a digital pH meter (keeping the other circuit open) and from a microammeter (keeping the other circuit closed), respectively. The electrical parameters in between these two extreme values (V_{oc} and i_{sc}) were determined with the help of a carbon pot (log 500 k) connected in the circuit of microammeter through which an external load in the circuit was applied. The results are summarized in Table 1. It was observed that in all these cases, *i-V* curves deviated from their expected regular rectangular shape. The power point (a point on the curve where the product of potential and current is maximum) in these *i-V* curves were determined and their fill factor (η) were also calculated using relation :

$$\eta = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}}$$

The performance (storage capacity) of the photogalvanic cells containing ascorbic acid – three type of dyes systems were studied by applying the desired external load

to have the potential and current corresponding to power point, after removing the source of illumination. It was quite interesting to observe that the performance of the cell in dark was affected appreciably in the presence of dyes. A comparison of performance is given in Table 1 and the order of performance of these cells in dark in presence of various types of dyes was as follows :

Methylene blue > Safranin > Rhodamine B

The conversion efficiency of all these photogalvanic systems were calculated using the electrical output at power point and the power of incident radiations. The systems (at their optimum conditions) were also exposed to sunlight. The conversion efficiency and sunlight conversion data for these photogalvanic cells are reported in Table 1. On the basis of observed data, the photogalvanic cells containing different type of dyes have the decreasing efficiency in the order :

Methylene blue > Safranin > Rhodamine B

Mechanism :

On the basis of these observations, a tentative mechanism has also been proposed for the generation of photocurrent in these photogalvanic cells as :

On irradiation dye molecules get excited form

The excited dye molecules accept an electron from reductant and converted into semi or leuco form of dye, and the reductant into its oxidized form.

At platinum electrode, the semi or leuco form of dye loses an electron and converted into original dye molecule.

Table 1. *i-V* Characteristics of the cell, performance and conversion efficeincy of dye-combinating

[Ascorbic acid] = $4.8 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Methylene blue] = $3.2 \times 10^{-6} M$, [Safranin] = $4.0 \times 10^{-6} M$, [Rhodamine B] = $4.1 \times 10^{-6} M$, Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , Temp. = 303 K

System	V_{oc} (mV)	i_{sc} (μA)	V_{pp} (mV)	i_{pp} (μA)	η	Power (μW)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	Efficiency (%)	Conversion data	
									Potential (mV)	Current (μA)
I	1121.0	165.0	864.0	100.0	0.46	148.66	165	0.83	2703	495
II	1061.0	150.0	804.0	150.0	0.42	120.60	115	0.65	2412	450
III	1137.0	120.0	812.0	65.0	0.38	59.64	45	0.51	1491	495

Systems : Ascorbic acid and Methylene blue (I), Safranin (II), Rhodamine B (III).

At counter electrode, Dye molecules accept an electron from electrode and converted in semi or leuco form.

Finally leuco/semi form of dye and oxidised form of reductant combine to give original dye and reductant molecule and the cycle will go on.

where D, D⁻, R and R⁺ are dyes semi/leuco form of the dye, reductant and its oxidised form, respectively.

Conclusions :

On the basis of observed data, the photogalvanic cells containing Ascorbic acid-Methylene blue system was the most suitable due to be used in these cells from conversion efficiency and storage capacity point of view and these are competently followed by systems containing Ascorbic acid-Safranin and Ascorbic acid-Rhodamine B systems.

Over all the Methylene blue containing photogalvanic cell are efficient enough from solar energy conversion as well as in its storage.

Experimental

Ascorbic acid (Sigma), Methylene blue, Safranin and Rhodamine B (s.d. fine), and sodium hydroxide (s.d. fine) were used in the present work. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water and were kept in amber coloured containers. Concentrations of Ascorbic acid, $4.8 \times 10^{-3} M$, Methylene blue $3.2 \times 10^{-6} M$, Safranin

$4.0 \times 10^{-6} M$, Rhodamine B $4.2 \times 10^{-6} M$, respectively. A mixture of solution of the dyes, reductant and sodium hydroxide was placed in a H-type glass tube. A platinum electrode ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) placed in one limb of the H-tube and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) in the other limb of the H-tube. The whole system was first placed in dark till a stable potential was attained, then the limb containing platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp and the limb containing SCE was kept in dark. A water fitter was placed between the exposed limb and the light source to cut off infra-red radiations.

The photochemical bleaching of dyes were studied potentiometrically. An Agronic 511 pH meter and OSAW microammeter were used to measure the potential and current generated by the system, respectively. The current voltage characteristics were determined by applying external load with the help of carbon pot (log 500 Ω) connected in the circuit. The effect of variation of different parameters on electrical parameters was studied in detail.

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